

A Comparative Study of Remote Sensing Techniques for Bathymetric Data Acquisition in Lokoja, Kogi State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study successfully performed a comparative study of remote sensing techniques for bathymetric data acquisition in Lokoja, Kogi state Nigeria. The following objectives were achieved by acquiring the multi bands of Landsat 8, Sentinel -2 and MODIS imagery used for bathymetric processing, acquiring remotely sensed images and extracting bathymetric information using different remote sensing techniques and comparatively analyzing the accuracies obtained between the remote sensing techniques and ground-based bathymetry. The methodology involved the acquisition of multi-sensor images, acquisition of sounding data, image preprocessing, water depth extraction models and validation using sounding data and correlation coefficient. The results revealed that the bathymetric mapping using Stumpf's ratio on Landsat 8 imagery gave depth values ranging from 0 – 0.18m classified as very shallow, 0.18m – 0.43m classified as shallow, 0.43m – 0.55m classified as deep and 0.55m – 1m classified as very deep. Results from using Stumpf's ratio on Sentinel-2 imagery gave depth values ranging from 0 – 0.23m classified as very shallow, 0.23m – 0.45m classified as shallow, 0.45m – 0.57m classified as deep and 0.57m – 1m classified as very deep. Results from using Stumpf's ratio on MODIS gave depth values ranged from 0 – 0.12m classified as very shallow, 0.12m – 0.29m classified as shallow, 0.29m – 0.46m classified as deep and 0.46m – 58m classified as very deep. Also, the results from bathymetric mapping using Dierssen's ratio on Landsat 8 imagery gave depth values ranging from 0 – 0.21m classified as very shallow, 0.21m – 0.38m classified as shallow, 0.38m – 0.58m classified as deep and 0.58m – 1m classified as very deep. Results from using Dierssen's ratio on Sentinel-2 imagery gave depth values ranging from 0 – 0.25m classified as very shallow, 0.25m – 0.48m classified as shallow, 0.48m – 0.57m classified as deep and 0.57m – 1m classified as very deep. Results from using Dierssen's ratio on MODIS gave depth values ranging from 0 – 0.13m classified as very shallow, 0.13m – 0.30m classified as shallow, 0.30m – 0.49m classified as deep and 0.49m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 562 m², shallow covered an area of 679m², deep zone covered an area of 972m², while very deep covered an area of 175m². The validation results using correlation coefficient and sounding data, revealed that Stumpf's Band ratio performed better than Dierssen's Band ratio. Therefore, Stumpf's band ratio method is recommended as a viable method for satellite based bathymetric mapping as it performed better than Dierssen's band ratio when compared with the validation data.

Keywords: Bathymetry; Remote Sensing; GIS; Kogi State; Water Depth

1. Introduction

In Lokoja, Kogi state the only source of bathymetric information is through traditional means; employing the use of echo sounder, but this method is often expensive and can only cover a small area at a time. The use of remote sensing facilitates wide coverage and synoptic analyses over a short period of time; such data will provide an extensive reliable bathymetric information cover a wide area.

In previous studies, most of these bathymetry retrieval algorithms are reportedly practical in clear ocean waters (1, 2). These techniques have proven itself as a useful reconnaissance tool of near-shore bathymetric mapping (3, 4) and coastal monitoring in shallow water (5). According to (6), imagery-derived bathymetry has been utilized in nautical charting by some hydrographic offices as it is capable and accomplished to meet the total vertical uncertainty (TVU) specification as stated in the IHO's S-44 Classification of Surveys.

Nonetheless, this topic is relatively new and still less-explored in Lokoja, Kogi State, therefore, this study takes the initiative to examine different remotely sensed-derived bathymetry approaches to estimate the bathymetric depths along the River Niger from Jamata Bridge along Abuja Road North East to Lokoja capital of Kogi state. This will provide an alternative for bathymetric information over a large area.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study Area

Lokoja is a city in Nigeria which lies at the confluence of the Niger and Benue Rivers. It is the capital of Nigeria’s Kogi State; a state carved out from Kwara and Benue State in 1991. It is bounded by the Niger in the North and East upstream from the capital until the border with Kwara State and includes the city of Lokoja with latitude 07°42’N to 07° 52’N and Longitude 06°38’E to 06°41’E. It is also a Local Government Area of Kogi State with an area of 3,180km² and a population of 195,261 at the 2006 census. See fig 1.

Figure 1: Map of Owerri (Study Area)

Although the area has been inhabited for thousands of years, the present settlement at Lokoja was established in 1857 by the British explorer William Baikie at the site of an earlier model farm constructed during the failed Niger expedition of 1841. Lokoja was the capital of the British Northern Nigeria protectorate and remained a convenient administrative town for the British Colonial government after the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Nigeria. In 1914, the first Governor General sir Fredrick Lugard governed the new Nation Nigeria from Lokoja.

2.2 Materials

The data utilized to achieve the aim and objectives of this study are categorized into primary and secondary data sources.

2.2.1 Primary Data

Primary data were gathered through field visits specific to this study. These included the collection of sounding data from a section of the River Niger. Sounding data involve measuring the depth of water bodies to understand underwater topography and are crucial for accurate bathymetric studies.

2.2.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data comprised satellite imagery from various sources. Specifically, the study used Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI), Sentinel-2, and Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) imageries. These imageries were obtained from the United States Geological Survey's Earth Explorer website (www.earthexplorer.usgs.gov). The satellite images provide critical data for remote sensing analysis and environmental monitoring.

2.3 Methods

The methods employed in this study involve a series of steps for image preprocessing and data analysis to correct for atmospheric errors and estimate bathymetric depth.

2.3.1 Image Preprocessing

Image preprocessing was conducted to correct atmospheric errors in the satellite imageries. Atmospheric correction is essential to eliminate distortions caused by the atmosphere's influence on the captured images. The algorithm developed by Gordon et al. (1983) and refined by Stumpf and Pennock (1989) for several remote sensors, such as the Coastal Zone Color Scanner, Advanced Very High-Resolution Radiometer, and Landsat Thematic Mapper, was employed for this purpose.

2.3.2 Bathymetric Depth Estimation

To estimate bathymetric depth, the study utilized the simplified linear regression algorithm developed by Stumpf et al. (2003). This algorithm determines the bathymetric depth (Z) using two tunable constant coefficients (m_0 and m_1) and a ratio of the observed reflectance of two consecutive bands (R_i and R_j). The model uses the division of observed reflectance log values to estimate water depth. This method was applied to the study area to estimate bathymetric depths.

Additionally, Dierssen et al. (2003) developed a similar band-ratio concept to estimate bathymetric depth, which was also employed in this study. This model differs slightly by modeling the difference between observed reflectance log values. The estimated water depth is calculated from two tunable constant coefficients (m_0 and m_1) and a log-difference between the observed reflectance of two consecutive bands (R_i and R_j).

2.3.3 Validation and Analysis

To validate the results obtained from applying Stumpf and Dierssen's ratio models, correlation coefficient analysis and sounding data were used. The raster results from the models were imported into ArcGIS. The coordinates from the sounding data were utilized to extract values from the raster using the "value to multi points" tool in ArcGIS. This process involved extracting the depth values from Stumpf's ratio and Dierssen's ratio models using the coordinates acquired from sounding data. The depth values obtained from the models were then compared to those obtained from sounding data to ensure accuracy and reliability.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bathymetric Mapping using Stumpf's Ratio

Bathymetric mapping using Landsat 8 imagery had depth values ranging from 0 – 0.18m classified as very shallow, 0.18m – 0.43m classified as shallow, 0.43m – 0.55m classified as deep and 0.55m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 300 m², shallow covered an area of 530m², deep covered an area of 693m², while very deep covered an area of 865m². Results from Sentinel-2 imagery had depth values ranging from 0 – 0.23m classified as very shallow, 0.23m – 0.45m classified as shallow, 0.45m – 0.57m classified as deep and 0.57m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 323m², shallow covered an area of 507m², deep covered an area of 883m², while very deep covered an area of 675m². Results from MODIS had depth values ranged from 0 – 0.12m classified as very shallow, 0.12m – 0.29m classified as shallow, 0.29m – 0.46m classified as deep and 0.46m – 58m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 572 m², shallow covered an area of 685m², deep covered an area of 973m², while very deep covered an area of 158m². See figure 2 for details.

Figure 2: Bathymetry depths derived from Landsat 8 OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS using Stumpfs ratio

3.2. Bathymetric Mapping using Dierssen’s Ratio

Bathymetric mapping using Landsat 8 imagery had depth values ranging from 0 – 0.21m classified as very shallow, 0.21m – 0.38m classified as shallow, 0.38m – 0.58m classified as deep and 0.58m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 380 m², shallow covered an area of 500m², deep covered an area of 673m², while very deep covered an area of 835m². Results from Sentinel-2 imagery had depth values ranging from 0 – 0.25m classified as very shallow, 0.25m – 0.48m classified as shallow, 0.48m – 0.57m classified as deep and 0.57m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 343m², shallow covered an area of 527m², deep covered an area of 853m², while very deep covered an area of 665m². Results from MODIS had depth values ranging from 0 – 0.13m classified as very shallow, 0.13m – 0.30m classified as shallow, 0.30m – 0.49m classified as deep and 0.49m – 1m classified as very deep. The very shallow zone covered an area of 562 m², shallow covered an area of 679m², deep covered an area of 972m², while very deep covered an area of 175m². See figure 3 for details.

Figure 3: Bathymetry depths derived from Landsat 8 OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS using Dierssens ratio

3.3. Validation of Bathymetric Mapping using Sounding Data

In order to determine the similarities between the Stumpfs ratio and Dierssen ratio derived results and the sounding data derived results, each of the depth levels were extracted and a cross section across each level were calculated to determine the closeness of each of the results of bathymetric models to the sounding data. This is shown in figure 4 – 9.

Figure 4: Correlation between Landsat 8 OLI derived depth (Stumps Ratio) and sounding data

Figure 5: Correlation between Sentinel-2 derived depth (Stumps Ratio) and sounding data

Figure 6: Correlation between MODIS derived depth (Stumpfs Ratio) and sounding data

Figure 7: Correlation between Landsat 8OLI derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data

Figure 8: Correlation between Sentinel-2 derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data

Figure 9: Correlation between MODIS derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data

From figures 4 – 9, the results obtained from using Stumpf's band ratio on Landsat 8OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS images were tested and validated using correlation coefficient and sounding data, the validation test gave a correlation coefficient of 0.6715 for the relationship between Landsat 8OLI derived depth (Stumpf's Ratio) and sounding data which indicated a good relationship. The validation test also gave a correlation coefficient of 0.6319 for the relationship between Sentinel-2 derived depth (Stumpf's Ratio) and sounding data which also indicated a good relationship with the validation data. Lastly, the relationship between MODIS derived depth (Stumpf's Ratio) and sounding data gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5661 which also indicates a good relationship with the validation data. The results obtained from using Dierssen's band ratio on Landsat 8OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS images were also tested and validated using correlation coefficient and sounding data, the validation test gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5661 for the relationship between Landsat 8OLI derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data which indicated a good relationship. The validation test also gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5430 for the relationship between Sentinel-2 derived

depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data which also indicated a good relationship with the validation data. Lastly, the relationship between MODIS derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5108 which also indicates a good relationship with the validation data.

4. Conclusion

Bathymetry mapping is important for seabed morphology studies, environmental research, and resource management of coastal zones. Conventional approaches to bathymetry mapping rely on field surveys of water depth at sampled locations. Such approaches are however characterized as being labor-intensive and time-consuming (Liu et al. 2003). Moreover, it is often difficult to achieve the desired mapping accuracy just based on a limited number of sampled points. Hence, this study successfully performed a comparative study of remote sensing techniques for bathymetric data acquisition in Lokoja, Kogi state Nigeria.

The results obtained from using Stumpf's band ratio on Landsat 8OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS images were tested and validated using correlation coefficient and sounding data, the validation test gave a correlation coefficient of 0.6715 for the relationship between Landsat 8OLI derived depth (Stumpfs Ratio) and sounding data which indicated a good relationship. The validation test also gave a correlation coefficient of 0.6319 for the relationship between Sentinel-2 derived depth (Stumpfs Ratio) and sounding data which also indicated a good relationship with the validation data. Lastly, the relationship between MODIS derived depth (Stumpfs Ratio) and sounding data gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5661 which also indicates a good relationship with the validation data.

Also, the results obtained from using Dierssen's band ratio on Landsat 8OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS images were tested and validated using correlation coefficient and sounding data, this gave a correlation coefficient of 0.6319 for the relationship between Landsat 8OLI derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data which indicated a good relationship. The validation test also gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5430 for the relationship between Sentinel-2 derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data which also indicated a good relationship with the validation data. Lastly, the relationship between MODIS derived depth (Dierssen's Ratio) and sounding data gave a correlation coefficient of 0.5108 which also indicates a good relationship with the validation data. The study was able extract water depths from Landsat 8 OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS images, however, for cases where precision is of the essence sounding using dual beam echo sounder is still recommended as the results gotten from Landsat 8 OLI, Sentinel-2 and MODIS only describes the relative depths; they do not depict absolute depths and cannot be used for navigation purposes.

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